

MODERN MANAGER QUALITIES

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Abstract: In this article, the leader is the person responsible, responsible for what the qualities of the personnel should be, what is the need to focus on in the management of personnel, from the big problems of the leadership team to the success of zarraday. The leader is an elegant employee who has a reputation in the community, who can follow people with his attitude, attitude. The leader has the ability to influence the members of the team, there has been talk of uniting the members of the team.

Key words: management, leader, employee, work, quality, team, agility, productivity, result, culture, knowledge, specialist, conditions, purpose, term.

From the big problems of the leadership team to zarraday responsible for the success, responsible person. The leader is a reputation in the team-notice, treat, follow people with an attitude of work an intelligent employee who takes. Influence on leading team members have the ability, bring team members together and lead a maslak sari takes. The leader is far-sighted and exalted for the benefit of the community creates ideas. With a difference between leadership and leadership, they are interrelated in the interests and interests of the community, one is filling the latter. It is not always possible to distinguish them from each other does not lead to an effective result, the reason is the leading work with the leader there will be people who care equally for their effectiveness. Creating leading innovative innovations, advancing new ideas it makes a lot of use of the method of encouraging the team during push-ups. Leaders at the same time in the team between employees find time for problems with a relationship, production character do not receive, therefore, informal "leaders" of organizations we told above about the need for calculated leaders. A team that can find easy solutions to a number of issues in the management process leaders who can find a sincere language, just like their employees very important to the management process, often used side by side in the teran content of the concepts of " leader "and" leader " to each other the image of working and selfless people who work in faith eye before us is embodied. Leaders

who have great respect in their work activities are truly also become the rightful pillars of the team, this is how it is there are reasons:

Leaders which are always applied, because the team applies it;

The achievement of the leader-the confidence of the team in him is great;

The friend of the leader is many, because he understands everyone, applies;

What is a leader?and why?if he asks;

Leader original creates ideas, the reason is all in the community can quickly get along with talented employees;

The activities of the leader – in the quick progress of the opinion of the team

The task of the leader is to plan, organize work and set tasks consists of dividing.

The leader leads the process of implementation of the plans;

There are employees subordinate to the leader / ;

The leader's choice is in the system and organization of the clock;

The leader organizes, supervises the management process. Modern management trends leadership – other describes it as influencing people. Taking this point of view

looking at, the leadership influence of the leader makes the whole team in its application, to the problem of each employee, his own problem to the pain, pain looks like deb. It is possible to gain affection by not giving affection to the people the absence is reflected in this leading activity. Again in Management Science according to other approaches, leadership is management status, the leader is described as a career. Soul for the organization leadership to man by performing management tasks achieves the status. For this reason, no leader is appointed, it is not marked, it is formed. One can look at the appointment of leaders, the election of leaders if we are, of course, the tasks of the leaders of this category are also very difficult we make sure that. After all, the leaders are a holistic group of the team they combine in the form, at the right time, acceptable political decisions in their place

they are not afraid to accept, control in a friendly and impartial way they carry out the commonality of goals in the organization Tegra they try to provide. The main activities of the adult are personnel disputes, personnel successes, employee dissatisfaction, employee incentives, punishment of employees (of course, if there is enough reason for this), to employees it consists of giving motivation and relentless movement in this ASNO is. There are also such events that a number of employees are undesirable leading decisions will either occur with a word and a hint, or nap. The

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support of the leader is the service of the leader and it has a huge impact on the increase in respect. Organization leaders, managers official in organizations

leaders are informal when they function in a relationship take over the relationship. Their working capacity is mainly the organization to lead employees in matters that underlie their success, and the result will be persuasion to the effect. Leadership betartib elimination of processes, on the basis of the approved Charter of the organization support for general leadership, stability towards a clear goal, goals, moods of employees, to work positive impact on relationships, interests, universal capabilities shows. After all, leadership can be punished or encouraged no, because such an opportunity will be only in official leaders, but leaders who have their place in the organization will have the opportunity to support and inspire employees all the time. Non-official documents, known legal-meory leaders who do not respond to documents are relatively narrower social for being a representative in the circle, in society, his powers are also wide, the possibilities of activity are also less than that of an official leader. The leader is never alone, he is always an organization will be among his employees, he will urge employees to take one or another action. Because the role of leading employees in the organization, their moods, they know their aspirations, interests, etc. better than everyone else, they are inside is considered the most initiator. Simply an example. Organization staff the most enterprising in their ranks, ready to help others, sharp intelligent, intellectual leaders who can pass on to everyone, the most humorous soul beggars, who can understand others — emotional bold, able to encourage the presence of leaders, employees to work, they know that they have resolute comrades and in many cases lean on him. Every leader who has earned a reputation for his work, mehru attitude will be the pride of the organization. This is the reason leading other persons ability to exert both emotional-emotional and volitional influenceowner. People find a way to cheer them up, understand them in different situations the lifetime of leaders who gain confidence and the like reputation enrich the content. Entrepreneur and businessman in the management process leaders give informal leaders even in the most delicate and difficult situations they lean.

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